

ISic4390

Fragmentary early Christian funerary inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2019-09-13 - Jonathan Prag created the file based upon the ed.pr.

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

The inscription was (re)discovered in the site stores, and its original provenance is not recorded. Based upon its re-use in a late antique opus sectile floor, Tréziny speulates that it may have come from the area of the Cantera lighthouse , but this will already have been secondary deposition.

Coordinates

37.205079, 15.184089

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, Antiquarium di Megara Hyblaia

Physical Description

Four fragments of a green marble plaque, re-used in a polychrome opus sectile pavement. Part of the upper margin is preserved, as well as the right margin of the text. The fourth, separate fragment, preserves part of the left margin, but its relationship to the other fragments is unclear. Most of the left and all of the lower parts of the text are lost. Dimensions record max height and width of the surviving, joining, three fragments.

Dimensions

Height 22 cm

Width 40 cm

Depth 2.9 cm

Layout

Remains of three lines of Greek letters, with small space to the margin at top, and vacat to the right and a roughly consistent right margin, suggesting line ends are preserved. The letters on the fourth fragment are smaller, and preserve vacat to the left suggesting line beginning. A further line is partially preserved on the fourth fragment.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are fairly regularly cut, with almost no serifs/terminations to the strokes, except for the slight extension of the apex of alpha and delta. Alpha has broken bar; omicron is slightly ovoid and full size; pi has equal length verticals; epsilon is lunate; phi is rhomboid.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 12 mm

Line 2: 12-14 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 2 mm

Interlineation line 2 to 3: 1-2 mm

Text

Apparatus

Text of Tréziny 2011

Tréziny: alternatively φλ

Translation (en)

[name] ... the infant, who died on the fifth day before the Ides(?) of September, having lived...

Commentary

The restorations are to some extent *exempli gratia*, since e.g. the Kalends is possible instead of the Ides, and October and November are also possible restorations for the month. It is not clear where the second fragment fits in (the letters are smaller, but the marble is the same). Although Tréziny suggest lambda is also possible, from the photograph alpha looks reasonably certain. As Tréziny notes, there appears to be a vacat after the second letter.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Tréziny, Henry 2011. À propos d'une inscription funéraire paléochrétienne de Mégara Hyblaea. *Provence Historique. Hommages à Jean Guyon*. 61: 127-134. At 127-129 with fig.1

Tréziny, Henry 2018. Mégara Hyblaea. 7, La ville classique, hellénistique et romaine. *CEFR*. Rome. At 283-284 with fig.422

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